

Spectral Graph Pruning for Context Optimization in Retrieval-Augmented Generation

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Abstract—Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) has become the dominant paradigm for grounding Large Language Models (LLMs) in external knowledge. Despite their effectiveness, RAG systems suffer from the context bottleneck: retrieved content fills the model’s context window with semantically similar but structurally redundant segments, increasing inference costs, latency, and degrading multi-hop reasoning performance. Existing context compression methods primarily operate on token-level statistical measures and fail to account for the global structural dependencies present in long-form documents. We present Spectral Graph Pruning (SGP), a graph-based framework for context optimization that preserves structural information. SGP models retrieved content as a heterogeneous semantic graph and applies query-biased spectral centrality analysis—specifically, a Tikhonov-regularized Laplacian smoothing formulation with thermal personalization—to identify structurally significant segments. Rather than discarding locally uninformative tokens, SGP retains the topological backbone of the document, maintaining narrative coherence while eliminating redundant context. According to experiments run on 200 multi-hop reasoning questions sampled from the HotpotQA and MuSiQue datasets, the SGP approach achieves 47.7% context compression while retaining 94.5% of Token F1 scores of full contexts (0.706 vs. 0.747). In all comparison experiments across different metrics such as Token F1, Exact Match, ROUGE-L, BERTScore, and Answer Coverage, SGP outperforms Dense Retrieval for similar levels of compression rates. These results demonstrate that structure-aware spectral graph analysis provides a more effective context compression strategy than similarity-based retrieval approaches for multi-hop RAG systems.

Index Terms—Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), Large Language Models (LLMs), Graph Signal Processing, Spectral Graph Theory, Context Compression, Query-Biased PageRank, Multi-Hop Reasoning, Tikhonov Regularization

I. INTRODUCTION

Language models with huge capacities have completely changed the document intelligence, knowledge synthesis, and enterprise search areas. The state-of-the-art models like GPT-4 [13], Gemini [12], and Llama 3 [21] demonstrate the ability to reason effectively even when the text is disorganized. However, when integrated with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) architectures, these models face a primary issue which is called the *context-cost trade-off*.

Current LLM models offer context windows with ranges between thousands and millions of tokens, but they do not make effective use of this ability. The key feature of transformer-based [11] LLMs – the self-attention operation – scales quadratically $O(n^2)$ with input size, which makes inference costly and inefficient for lengthy contexts. In addition, empirical studies have highlighted a phenomenon referred to as *lost-in-the-middle* [2], wherein model performance degrades when relevant information is embedded within long, noisy contexts—suggesting that simply increasing retrieved tokens can diminish the signal-to-noise ratio rather than improve reasoning.

In modern RAG workflows, the most common method used for retrieval purposes is retrieve-and-rank [1]. According to this approach, documents are segmented, embedded in vectors, and ranked based on the cosine similarity with respect to the user’s query. While successful in retrieving factoids, this approach shows some degree of structural insensitivity. Namely, vector similarity operates under the assumption that individual

document fragments are autonomous; thus, structural relations are not taken into account during retrieval. For example, when a financial report mentions an income number, such a statement is meaningful if the periods are specified, along with other details provided in separate segments of the document. A similar retrieval technique will be able to extract the factoid but ignore the crucial information or produce several identical summaries without bridging.

To address these limitations, we propose **Spectral Graph Pruning (SGP)**, a post-retrieval context optimization framework grounded in graph signal processing. Rather than scoring segments independently, SGP models retrieved content as a heterogeneous semantic context graph and analyzes its spectral properties to determine structural importance. A query-biased centrality measure based on Tikhonov-regularized Laplacian smoothing is used to identify the minimal set of nodes that preserves narrative connectivity. This reframes the context compression as a topological optimization problem, allowing structure-aware pruning that reduces redundancy while maintaining the reasoning accuracy.

A. Contributions

The primary contributions of this work are:

- A heterogeneous context graph formulation that captures chunk-level, entity-level, and structural-level document relationships (Section III).
- A query-biased spectral scoring method using Tikhonov-regularized Laplacian smoothing with thermal personalization that propagates query relevance through document topology (Section III-B).
- An adaptive elbow-based pruning strategy with an entity safety constraint that prevents removal of semantically anchoring nodes (Section III-C).
- Empirical evaluation on 200 multi-hop queries across HotpotQA and MuSiQue, demonstrating that SGP achieves $\sim 47.7\%$ compression while retaining 94.5% of full-context reasoning performance and outperforming Dense Retrieval at comparable compression ratios (Section V).
- A fully reproducible open-source implementation [22].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The effective use of context in LLMs sits at the convergence of information retrieval, neural text generation, and graph-based modeling. Prior work relevant to this study can be organized into three areas: (i) structural constraints of RAG, (ii) statistical context compression methods, and (iii) graph-based reasoning frameworks in NLP.

A. The Contextual Bottleneck in RAG

Lewis et al. [1] introduced Retrieval-Augmented Generation, establishing a retriever-reader architecture to augment language models with external knowledge. Early implementations depended on embedding-based similarity search for dense vector retrieval. While effective for knowledge injection, further studies revealed the scalability constraints.

The lost-in-the-middle phenomenon, identified by Liu et al. [2], demonstrates that reasoning accuracy does not increase monotonically with context size. Specifically, accuracy can degrade when relevant information is surrounded by long and noisy context. This finding exposes a structural inefficiency in similarity-based retrieval pipelines: a larger number of retrieved chunks can reduce the signal-to-noise ratio and diminish effective recall precision. These results imply that context optimization methods must be sensitive to structural dependencies, not merely similarity scores.

B. Statistical Methods for Context Window Compression

To mitigate the quadratic computational complexity of Transformer self-attention, several works have proposed token-level compression methods. Jiang et al. [3] describe LLMIn-gua, which uses a smaller language model to estimate token-level perplexity and removes low self-information segments. Similarly, Li et al. [4] propose Selective Context, which uses attention weights to prune redundant lexical units.

While this strategy will certainly lead to fewer tokens, it will depend upon statistical data from a limited local context. This method makes an implicit assumption that if a token does not have high lexical novelty, then its importance for reasoning is insignificant. Although in multi-hop reasoning tasks, where connectivity is important, a structurally significant segment of text could be statistically insignificant.

C. Graph-Based Reasoning and Spectral Analysis

Graph-based modeling techniques have also received significant attention as means to reason about relational dependencies between natural language elements [5]. The QA-GNN architecture was developed by Yasunaga et al. [6], combining knowledge graphs with language models in order to perform reasoning over structured data. Most recently, Edge et al. [7] designed GraphRAG to utilize community detection in order to enhance retrieval and summarization performance for queries.

While such frameworks highlight the usefulness of graph representations, their goals focus on improving generation or retrieval quality rather than on optimizing context window usage. In fact, the application of spectral graph analysis towards context window optimization in RAG has yet to be explored. Chung [8] provided the solid mathematical foundations for Laplacian analysis and eigenvector centrality, and Schlöterer et al. [9] used spectral pruning within GNNs. In this study, the previous works' findings will be furthered by performing query-biased spectral centrality analysis of heterogeneous semantic context graphs, allowing the elimination of redundant context without loss of narrative flow.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed framework, Spectral Graph Pruning (SGP), treats context compression as a structural graph analysis problem rather than a token-level statistical filtering problem. The framework consists of three major components: (1) heterogeneous context graph construction, (2) query-biased spectral analysis, and (3) adaptive pruning with context reassembly. An overview of the pipeline is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Overview of the Spectral Graph Pruning (SGP) pipeline. Retrieved chunks are modeled as a heterogeneous context graph, scored via query-biased spectral centrality, pruned adaptively using energy-mass pruning, and reassembled into a compressed context for language model reasoning.

A. Heterogeneous Context Graph Construction

To model the structural dependencies present in retrieved documents, unstructured text is represented as a heterogeneous context graph. Formally, the graph is defined as $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of nodes and E is the set of weighted directed edges. Unlike traditional knowledge graphs focused on entity–relation triples, the proposed graph preserves both narrative structure and document organization.

1) *Node Types*: Three types of nodes represent different levels of document structure:

- **Chunk Nodes (C)**: Main chunks derived from the text through a window size of 256–512 tokens with 32-token overlapping. These nodes contain the main semantic information of the text.
- **Entity Nodes (N)**: Named entities (for instance, persons, organizations, dates, numeric values) obtained by utilizing spaCy [20]. The nodes act as semantic anchors connecting similar text chunks.
- **Structure Nodes (S)**: Metadata concerning the text, such as section headings and labels.

2) *Edge Types*: Several edge types encode different structural relationships:

- **Sequential Edges**: Represent sequential chunk nodes $C_i \rightarrow C_{i+1}$, representing the order of text reading, having the weight of 1.0.
- **Semantic Edges**: Bidirectional edges $C_i \leftrightarrow C_j$ added when the cosine similarity between embedding vectors exceeds the threshold $\tau = 0.80$, with Top- K sparse representation for avoiding hubs.
- **Entity Edges**: Directed edges $C_i \rightarrow N_k$ linking chunk nodes to extracted named entities, enabling multi-hop reasoning across text and entity nodes, weighted at 0.8.

B. Query-Biased Spectral Analysis

After graph construction, the relevance of each node with respect to the input query is estimated using a Tikhonov-regularized Laplacian smoothing formulation. This is more numerically stable than power-iteration PageRank [18] and has a closed-form solution.

Let A be the symmetrized weighted adjacency matrix of G , and D the corresponding degree matrix. The normalized graph Laplacian is:

$$L_{\text{norm}} = I - D^{-1/2} A D^{-1/2} \quad (1)$$

The importance vector \mathbf{r} is obtained by solving the Tikhonov-regularized system:

$$\mathbf{r} = (I + \mu L_{\text{norm}})^{-1} \mathbf{p} \quad (2)$$

where $\mu = \frac{\alpha}{1-\alpha} \cdot \lambda$ controls the degree of Laplacian smoothing (with $\alpha = 0.85$ and regularization strength $\lambda = 0.1$), and \mathbf{p} is the query-personalization vector. This formulation minimizes the objective:

$$\min_{\mathbf{r}} \|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{p}\|^2 + \mu \cdot \mathbf{r}^\top L_{\text{norm}} \mathbf{r} \quad (3)$$

balancing fidelity to the query signal against smoothness over the graph topology.

1) *Thermal Personalization Vector*: Unlike standard PageRank using uniform teleportation, SGP constructs \mathbf{p} dynamically from query Q using temperature-scaled softmax:

$$p_i = \frac{\exp(\cos \text{Sim}(\text{Node}_i, Q)/\tau)}{\sum_j \exp(\cos \text{Sim}(\text{Node}_j, Q)/\tau)} \quad (4)$$

Here, $\tau = 0.2$ is used for temperature. A lower value for temperature focuses more on those nodes that have high relevance to the query, whereas the softmax function ensures a proper probability distribution. Those nodes having high cosine similarity to the query obtain a higher initial importance, which then spreads across the structure of the graph, making possible for lexically dissimilar nodes with structurally relevant importance to gain importance via their structural neighborhood. Sentence embeddings are computed using `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` [19].

C. Adaptive Pruning Strategy

A fixed top- k selection is insufficient because query complexity varies across instances. SGP employs energy mass pruning:

- 1) **Ranking:** All chunk nodes $v \in V_C$ are ranked by spectral importance scores r_v .
- 2) **Cumulative Mass:** The cumulative importance distribution over ranked nodes is computed: $\text{cum}_k = \sum_{i=1}^k r_{(i)} / \sum_j r_j$.
- 3) **Elbow Detection:** The threshold k^* is identified as the minimal k such that $\text{cum}_{k^*} \geq \theta$, where $\theta = 0.65$ (energy mass target). This captures the most informative topological substructure.
- 4) **Safety Bounds:** k^* is clipped to $[\text{min_chunks}, \lfloor |V_C| \cdot r_{\max} \rfloor]$ where $\text{min_chunks} = 5$ and $r_{\max} = 0.6$.
- 5) **Pruning:** Nodes ranked below k^* are removed from the context graph.

1) *Entity Safety Constraint:* To prevent loss of critical semantic anchors, an entity node N_k is retained if it is connected to any retained chunk node C_i . This preserves entity definitions associated with retained text and prevents removal of essential semantic context.

D. Context Reassembly

After pruning, retained graph nodes are serialized back into linear text:

- 1) **Topological Ordering:** Retained chunk nodes are re-ordered by original document position to preserve narrative coherence.
- 2) **Context Bridging:** Where discontinuities exist between retained chunks, a delimiter `[. . .]` is inserted to signal omitted content to the language model.
- 3) **Serialization:** Ordered chunks are concatenated to produce the final compressed context.

The reference implementation of the SGP framework is publicly available [22].

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

A. Datasets

We evaluate SGP on two standard multi-hop reasoning benchmarks:

- **HotpotQA** [15] (distractor setting): Questions requiring reasoning over two Wikipedia articles, with distractor passages included to challenge retrieval precision. We use

the distractor setting specifically because the presence of noise passages most directly stresses context compression methods - a system that retains structurally irrelevant chunks will be penalized both in token budget and reasoning accuracy.

- **MuSiQue** [14]: Compositional multi-hop questions constructed from single-hop questions, requiring up to 4-hop reasoning chains. MuSiQue tests whether structural graph connectivity survives deeper reasoning requirements where bridging context across multiple hops is essential.

Both corpora were selected due to their applicability within the context of multi-hop reasoning because it is precisely there that the impact of contextual structures is largest, according to SGP. single-hop factoid-based benchmark tests cannot properly assess the dependency between the structures of the retrieved passages, which is why they are insufficiently challenging for graph-based compression. In general, HotpotQA and MuSiQue cover both different kinds of multi-hop reasoning: bridging entity chains for the former and compositional question decomposition for the latter, which ensures a comprehensive testing of the impact of SGP-based structural compression on various reasoning types. From each corpus, $N = 100$ test queries were taken from the train partition, giving $N = 200$ queries altogether, each consisting of a query, the answer, and context passages.

B. Baselines

SGP is compared against the following approaches:

- **Full Context:** All retrieved passages are concatenated and fed to the language model without compression.
- **Dense Retrieval:** Standard vector similarity retrieval retaining the top-50% most similar chunks (`top_k_ratio = 0.5`), using the same `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` encoder.

C. Implementation Details

All experiments use GPT-OSS-120B via the OpenRouter API with temperature set to 0 for deterministic outputs and a maximum of 256 output tokens. Sentence embeddings are computed with `all-MiniLM-L6-v2` [19] via sentence-transformers. Named entity recognition uses spaCy’s `en_core_web_sm` pipeline [20]. The SGP hyperparameters are: damping factor $\alpha = 0.85$, regularization $\lambda = 0.1$, semantic threshold $\tau = 0.80$, Top- K semantic edges $K = 3$, softmax temperature $\tau_s = 0.2$, energy mass target $\theta = 0.65$, minimum retained chunks = 5, maximum retention ratio = 0.60.

Total evaluation runtime (including model loading, LLM inference, and metric computation) was 26m34s for HotpotQA and 33m20s for MuSiQue.

All code, evaluation scripts, hyperparameter configurations, and result logs are publicly available at [22] to support full reproducibility of the reported results.

D. Evaluation Metrics

We report the following metrics, selected to cover both lexical and semantic answer quality, and both LLM-dependent and LLM-independent perspectives on compression quality:

- **Token F1** and **Exact Match (EM)**: Token-level F1 and exact string match between predicted and ground-truth answers, with articles and punctuation normalized. These are the standard HotpotQA evaluation metrics [15], enabling direct comparison with published baselines.
- **ROUGE-L** [17]: Longest common subsequence (LCS) F1 score computed on token level. This metric allows measuring sequence-level similarities other than simple n-gram overlaps and is useful when phrasing an answer requires sequential multi-token entities.
- **BERTScore F1** [16]: Semantic similarity between prediction and reference measured through contextual embedding similarity. This metric is able to detect instances in which the phrasing differs but the meaning is preserved, which is especially useful for multi-hop questions where answers can have several possible phrasings.
- **Answer Coverage**: Percentage of gold answer tokens present in the retained context, computed before LLM inference. This metric is model-independent: it measures whether compression preserves the evidence needed to answer the question, decoupling retrieval quality from LLM generation quality. A compression method can achieve high Answer Coverage while still producing a wrong answer due to LLM reasoning failures, and vice versa.
- **Compression Ratio**: Percentage of tokens removed from the uncompressed context.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Main Results

Table I presents the aggregated results across all 200 queries. SGP achieves 47.7% context compression while retaining 94.5% of full-context Token F1 (0.706 vs. 0.747) and 97.6% of full-context BERTScore (0.845 vs. 0.864). Across every metric, SGP outperforms Dense Retrieval at a comparable compression ratio (50%).

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON ACROSS CONTEXT COMPRESSION METHODS ($N = 200$)

Method	F1	EM	R-L	BERT	Cov.	Comp.
Full Context	0.747	0.625	0.747	0.864	0.965	0.0%
Dense Retrieval	0.687	0.580	0.685	0.824	0.869	51.8%
SGP (Ours)	0.706	0.610	0.706	0.845	0.861	47.7%

F1 = Token F1; EM = Exact Match; R-L = ROUGE-L; BERT = BERTScore F1; Cov. = Answer Coverage; Comp. = Compression Ratio. Results averaged over HotpotQA (distractor) and MuSiQue, $n = 100$ each.

B. Quality vs. Compression Trade-off

Figure 2 shows the relationship between answer quality metrics and compression rate across methods. SGP occupies a

favorable position on this trade-off curve: it achieves compression comparable to Dense Retrieval while maintaining substantially higher answer quality. The gap between SGP and Dense Retrieval (2.9 F1 points, 3.0 EM points, 2.1 BERTScore points) demonstrates that structural graph-based pruning is more effective than similarity-based chunk selection at equivalent compression levels.

Fig. 2. Quality metrics vs. compression ratio for Full Context, Dense Retrieval, and SGP. SGP achieves higher answer quality than Dense Retrieval at a comparable compression rate, demonstrating the benefit of structure-aware pruning.

C. Answer Coverage vs. Compression

Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between answer coverage and compression ratio. Answer Coverage measures whether the retained context actually contains the tokens of the gold answer—making it a model-independent measure of compression quality. SGP (0.861) achieves coverage nearly identical to Dense Retrieval (0.869) despite using different selection criteria, confirming that structural pruning does not disproportionately discard answer-bearing segments. Both compressed methods show a moderate reduction from the full-context ceiling (0.965), which is expected given that compression necessarily removes some content.

D. Dual-Axis Accuracy-Compression Trade-off

Figure 4 presents a dual-axis visualization of Token F1 and compression ratio, highlighting the Pareto efficiency of each method. SGP achieves a favorable balance: it compresses 47.7% of the context while losing only 5.5 absolute F1 points compared to full context (vs. Dense Retrieval losing 6.0 F1 points at 51.8% compression). This suggests that structure-aware pruning provides a more efficient compression path.

E. Latency Analysis

Figure 5 reports end-to-end processing latency broken down into graph/retrieval overhead and LLM inference time. SGP incurs a total latency of 6846 ms per query on average, compared to 5305 ms for Full Context and 5065 ms for Dense Retrieval. The ~ 1600 ms overhead attributable to graph construction, embedding, and spectral scoring is not recovered through

Fig. 3. Evidence Retention vs. Compression. SGP maintains coverage close to Dense Retrieval while using a structurally informed selection strategy. Coverage reductions from the full-context baseline are proportional to compression level.

Fig. 4. Dual-axis trade-off between Token F1 (left axis) and compression ratio (right axis). SGP achieves higher F1 than Dense Retrieval at comparable compression, confirming the value of graph-structural context selection.

reduced LLM inference time at the context sizes evaluated in this study.

The latency regression can be considered a fair tradeoff since SGP pays more in terms of preprocessing effort for higher quality per token in the compressed context. Whether this is a good tradeoff depends on the context. If latency is of paramount importance, Dense Retrieval would be the preferred choice. However, if one prioritizes reasoning accuracy, and small latency regressions are not an issue—e.g., in offline analysis tasks and enterprise knowledge search—then the improvements in quality that SGP provides are worth the extra effort. Furthermore, the overhead required for constructing the graph should be less relevant for larger context lengths, where the $O(n^2)$ self-attention cost of processing full contexts dominates the total inference time.

F. Analysis and Discussion

Why SGP outperforms Dense Retrieval at similar compression. Dense Retrieval selects chunks greedily by cosine similarity to the query, which can retain multiple redundant, near-duplicate passages while discarding bridging segments that have low lexical overlap with the query but are structurally necessary for multi-hop chains. SGP’s graph-based propagation mechanism allows importance to flow through structural

Fig. 5. End-to-end latency breakdown into graph/retrieval overhead and LLM inference time. SGP’s graph construction adds ~ 1600 ms overhead that is not offset by reduced LLM inference at the evaluated context sizes, resulting in higher total latency than both baselines.

edges, surfacing such bridging nodes even when their direct query similarity is low.

The role of thermal personalization. The temperature-scaled softmax ($\tau = 0.2$) sharpens the personalization distribution toward the most query-relevant nodes, ensuring that the Laplacian smoothing propagates a focused relevance signal rather than a diffuse one. This is in contrast to uniform-teleportation PageRank, which would spread importance more uniformly across the graph.

G. Limitations

Several limitations of the current evaluation should be acknowledged.

Dataset answer characteristics. Both HotpotQA and MuSiQue are short-answer multi-hop benchmarks where ground-truth answers are typically brief extractive spans - named entities, dates, or short noun phrases that appear verbatim or near-verbatim in the source passages. This characteristic favors token-level metrics such as Exact Match and Token F1, which reward direct string overlap. It also means that Answer Coverage is a relatively strong signal, since the gold answer is usually a contiguous token sequence present somewhere in the retrieved chunks.

This setting does not reflect long-form document question answering tasks where answers are generated summaries or paraphrases synthesized across multiple document chunks, and where no single passage contains the answer verbatim. In such settings, the benefit of preserving structural document relationships is likely more pronounced, since the LLM must synthesize across retained segments rather than locate a span. Conversely, metrics such as BERTScore and ROUGE-L become more discriminative than Exact Match in that regime. Evaluating SGP on long-form generation benchmarks remains an important direction for future work.

Scale of evaluation. The evaluation is conducted on $N = 200$ queries ($n = 100$ per dataset), which constitutes a preliminary empirical study. Larger-scale evaluation across

the full benchmark test splits is needed to confirm statistical reliability of the observed margins.

Single LLM evaluated. All experiments use GPT-OSS-120B via OpenRouter. Results may not generalize across model families or sizes; smaller models with tighter context budgets may benefit more from compression, while larger models with longer context windows may be less sensitive to it.

Pre-chunked evaluation contexts. The evaluation uses dataset-provided passages instead of end-to-end retrieval from a raw corpus. This creates a deterministic experimental setting for isolating the effects of context compression, but same is less representative of production RAG pipelines where retrieval quality, chunking strategy, and compression interact at the same time.

Latency overhead. As shown in Figure 5, SGP incurs higher end-to-end latency (6846 ms) compared to Full Context (5305 ms) and Dense Retrieval (5065 ms). The ~ 1600 ms graph construction and spectral scoring overhead is not recovered through reduced LLM inference time at the context sizes evaluated. SGP’s latency trade-off becomes more favorable at larger context sizes where quadratic self-attention costs dominate, but this was not directly evaluated.

Scalability of spectral solve. The Tikhonov formulation requires solving an $n \times n$ linear system, incurring $O(n^3)$ complexity in the dense case. This may be prohibitive for very large context graphs (e.g., >500 nodes). Approximate solvers such as conjugate gradient methods are a practical mitigation and are left for future work.

VI. CONCLUSION

The current work focuses on the bottleneck of context in Retrieval-Augmented Generative models. The Spectral Graph Pruning (SGP) framework reframes context compression as an optimization problem, using retrieved content as a heterogeneous semantic graph and applying query-biased Tikhonov-regularized Laplacian smoothing to identify the structurally important segments.

From our evaluation over 200 multi-hop queries on HotpotQA and MuSiQue we can see that SGP achieves 47.7% context compression while retaining 94.5% of full-context Token F1 performance. Notably, SGP consistently outperforms Dense Retrieval, the standard similarity-based compression baseline across Token F1, Exact Match, ROUGE-L, BERTScore, and Answer Coverage at comparable compression ratios.

Future work will explore several extensions. First, dynamic graph construction strategies that adapt edge thresholds to query and document characteristics. Second, extension to multimodal retrieval settings incorporating image and table nodes. Third, reinforcement learning for learning pruning thresholds directly from downstream task performance, removing manual calibration of the energy mass target. Fourth, approximate linear solvers (e.g., conjugate gradient) to scale the Tikhonov formulation to larger context graphs. Finally, evaluation on

broader benchmarks spanning multilingual and multi-domain reasoning tasks.

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